

IMPROVEMENT OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM BASED ON INNOVATIVE ACTIVITIES

Orifjonova Nodira

Student of group 301 of Sambram University of Jizzakh region

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11474021>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 24th May 2024

Accepted: 30th May 2024

Online: 31th May 2024

KEY WORDS

Higher education, modern technology, innovation, scientific potential, distance education system, information and communication technologies, science, quality education.

ABSTRACT

This article focuses on the issues of improving information technologies in the higher education system based on innovative activities. In this regard, today's life cannot be imagined without information media, including the Internet. The novelty and uniqueness of information communication technologies from the point of view of human development, they are almost Human activity penetrates into all spheres, it is possible to use them in unlimited places and purposes. Information about the fact that such information and communication technologies can overcome obstacles in the process of human development with unprecedented effectiveness in three directions.

Introduction: Today, we are witnessing the implementation of a number of positive changes in our country in terms of raising the educational system to a new level, improving the quality of teacher training based on advanced international standards and increasing the level of coverage of higher pedagogical education. In particular, the activities of several higher educational institutions specializing in the training of pedagogic personnel have been launched. Joint educational programs with foreign countries were organized in this field of education. The legal and normative basis for the development of higher pedagogical education has been perfectly created. This situation is the basis for increasing attention to the quality of personnel training in the field of pedagogy, the wide introduction of advanced foreign experience in the field, and the development of pedagogical education infrastructure.

It is known that today the paradigm of education is changing in the developed and developing countries of the world. Based on the Asian model of education, the educational process goes from giving theoretical knowledge to developing the skills of applying the knowledge in practice, based on information technology, independent development of students. is focused on the formation of learning skills. The Swiss World Economic Forum has announced the ranking of the fastest growing countries in the economy of the World Economic Forum. Based on the data of the World Bank's "Global Economic Development" in the period from 2014 to 2017, Uzbekistan is the 5th among the countries with the highest annual growth rate. The prospect of reforms in Uzbekistan is based not only on the existing experience, traditions and values of the country, but also on the use of advanced international

foreign experience. Today, the field of information technologies occupies an important place in the development of our republic. Over the past years, the policy of the government of the Republic of Uzbekistan regarding the wide introduction and development of information technologies in our country is showing its results. If we look at the economic figures, the results of the last year can be assessed as positive. The volume of total services provided in the ICT sector reached 10.6 trillion soums, showing a 104% increase. Communication and information services grew to \$176 million, i.e. up to 130%.

ON MEASURES FOR FURTHER IMPROVEMENT OF THE EDUCATION SYSTEM IN THE FIELD OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES, DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH AND THEIR INTEGRATION WITH THE IT INDUSTRY

Improving the system of personnel training in the field of information technologies is one of the important conditions for the successful implementation of the "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy, the development of digital technologies and the wide implementation of them in the daily life of the population.

The measures taken to increase the efficiency of the system of vocational training and retraining in the field of information technologies create a solid foundation for providing state bodies and network organizations with qualified IT specialists.

In particular, a school specialized in in-depth teaching of information and communication technologies named after Muhammad al-Khorazmi and branches of a number of foreign universities have been launched, and digital technology training centers are being gradually established in districts and cities. .

At the same time, the lack of qualified personnel in the labor market of the republic requires the improvement of educational programs and methods in the field of information technologies and the strengthening of cooperation between educational institutions and IT companies.

In particular, in order to reform management in higher education institutions, to speed up the work carried out in the system, our president Shavkat Mirziyoyev. On July 11, 2019 approved Resolution No. PQ-4391 **"On measures to introduce new management principles into the system of higher and secondary special education"**. In the decision, "...higher educational institutions, personnel economic stimulation of the work of managerial, technical, service and educational support staff of retraining and advanced training centers, ensuring an increase in the amount of remuneration for their work, improving management activities in the system of higher and secondary special vocational education, introducing an effective management system" It is necessary to improve the management system of higher education institutions in order to ensure the performance of the specified tasks. In improving the management system, it is necessary to develop a unique mechanism, that is, to create a management mechanism that encourages the movement of all links in the system based on an innovative approach. It is impossible to increase the effectiveness of the heads of management departments, scientific and pedagogical personnel in higher education institutions without sufficient scientific and managerial potential. Therefore, it is necessary to pay attention to the existing scientific potential of educational institutions when applying management mechanisms. Without determining the scientific and management potential in higher education institutions, the use of the management mechanism may not allow to achieve the

goals of system improvement. In such cases, it is appropriate to develop mechanisms in accordance with the existing scientific potential of the educational institution and the management potential of the management units. Institutions of higher education establish an executive mechanism as an object of management based on regulatory legal documents, management methods and tools adopted by the management entity. In the process of ensuring the implementation, the organizational and economic mechanism of management is of great importance. In the internal management system, the leadership of the higher education institution participates as a management entity and distributes tasks according to the main activities and prospective plans to the management departments. It is in this process that it is necessary to organize "Innovation process" in the organizational-economic mechanism of management and activate its participation. As a result of making a decision in the "innovative process" and ensuring its implementation, the results of "innovative management" and "innovative education" are created. In order to increase the activity of the innovation process, to optimize the organizational and economic mechanism in management, to increase the efficiency of execution and to increase the accuracy of achieving the intended goal, it is necessary to establish an "Innovative management" department in higher education institutions. This department serves as the most important link in the management of higher education institutions with optimal work of the organizational and economic mechanism, increasing the activity of all departments, a new approach to each management process, constant application of management principles, and monitoring of full implementation. As a result, higher educational institutions achieve the efficiency of innovative management, organize effective management based on high scientific potential, competitive personnel, organizational efficiency and innovative approaches, and optimal functioning of the organizational and economic mechanism of innovative management in the higher educational institution is ensured.

Conclusions and suggestions: In conclusion, it is worth noting that the organizational-economic mechanism in the educational system should serve to ensure the organizational and economic efficiency of the educational institution, to achieve competitive personnel training, to have a superior position among other educational institutions.

It is proposed to carry out the following measures to effectively organize an innovative organizational and economic mechanism in the higher education system:

- on the basis of the developed "Organizational-economic mechanism of innovative management of higher educational institutions", it is necessary to reduce the "Dean's Office" division in the management structure and instead introduce the position of "Department Administrator" for each department, thereby optimizing management;

- it is necessary to form a structure in the form of interdependent systems and to organize a mechanism that ensures mutual movement in the coordination of the activities of the management departments of the educational institution;

- establishment of the "Innovative management" department, which ensures the integration of management departments;

- it is necessary to ensure continuity of use of international and local experiences affecting the quality of education;

- carrying out exemplary and critical analyzes of the activities of regular units in the councils of the institution using analytical methods;
- it is necessary to create an innovative environment and an innovative management mechanism in the higher education system;
- it is necessary to accelerate the activities of professional development and internship abroad, which serve to increase the labor potential of professors and teachers;
- it is necessary to constantly determine the effectiveness of innovative management in the institution and make operational decisions on shortcomings.

References:

1. Хужамкулов, Д. (2020). ХОРИЖИЙ ИНВЕСТИЦИЯЛАРНИ ЎЗБЕКИСТОН ИҚТИСОДИЁТГА ЖАЛБ ЭТИШ МАСАЛАЛАРИ. *Архив научных исследований*, (22).
2. Хужамкулов, Д. (2020). ҚИШЛОҚ ХУДУДЛАРИДА УЙ-ЖОЙЛАР ҚУРИЛИШИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ ВА МОЛИЯЛАШТИРИШНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ. *Архив научных исследований*, (22).
3. Khojamqulov, D., Yusupova, S., & Zayniddinov, R. (2019). Socio-economic development with foreign trade (trio of emerging markets, transition economy and investment attractiveness). *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (12), 425-434.
4. Хужамкулов, Д. (2020). ПЕНСИЯ ТАЪМИНОТИНИНГ ХОРИЖ ТАЖРИБАЛАРИ ВА ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ. *Архив научных исследований*, (21).
5. Khujamkulov, D. Y., Zayniddinov, R. K. O., Ergashev, D. R., Mamatov, M. A., & Uktamov, K. F. (2021). Improving the Use of Islamic Banking Services in Financing Investment Projects in Uzbekistan. *Revista geintec-gestao inovacao e tecnologias*, 11(2), 2205-2220.
6. Хужамкулов, Д. (2020). Совершенствования кредитования МСБ коммерческими банками Узбекистана. *Архив научных исследований*, (22).
7. Ismailova, N. (2019). Aspects of Modern Energy Saving Block Technology in House Building Sector of Uzbekistan. *Архив научных исследований*.
8. Ismailova, N. (2019). Aspects of Modern Energy Saving Block Technology in House Building Sector of Uzbekistan. *Архив научных исследований*.
9. Abdurakhmanov, K., Nurimbetov, R., Zikriyoev, A., & Khojamkulov, D. (2022, June). Comparison between correlation and latent model analysis on estimating causality of occupational health and safety in human capital development for raising economic efficiency (Evidence from building material manufacturing companies of Uzbekistan). In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 2432, No. 1). AIP Publishing.
10. Abdurakhmanov, K., Zikriyoev, A., Shadibekova, D., Khojamkulov, D., & Raimjanova, M. (2022, December). Limits and challenges of human resource technological talents in AI age. In *Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Future Networks & Distributed Systems* (pp. 202-209).
11. Маматов, Б., Носиров, Э., Хўжамкулов, Д., & Шарафхўжаева, К. (2007). Кичик бизнес ва хусусий тадбиркорлик лойиҳаларини молиялаштириш. *Ўқув қўлланма. ТМИ, 2007*.
12. Toshmurodova, M., Zikriyoev, A., Shadibekova, D., Khojamkulov, D., & Umarov, B. (2023, December). How Often Are Children on the Internet? Worldwide Prospective Multinomial

Logistic Regression. In *Proceedings of the 7th International Conference on Future Networks and Distributed Systems* (pp. 86-94).

13. Khujamkulov, D. (2023). DIGITIZATION AS A FACTOR IN THE FORMATION OF NEW ECONOMIC TECHNOLOGIES IN COMPETITIVE CONDITIONS. *Инновационные исследования в науке*, 2(12), 22-24.

14. Raxmatovna, R. M. (2024). The Importance of Speech Techniques in Assessing Students' Professional Potential Opportunities. *American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education* (2993-2769), 2(2), 98-100.

15. Rashidova, M. (2021). INGLIZ VA OZBEK TILLARIDA TRANSFORMATSIYA HODISASI. *Студенческий вестник*, (21-10), 48-49.

16. Rashidova, M. (2024, April). MODERN CONCEPTS AIMED AT INCREASING THE PROFESSIONAL POTENTIAL OF THE SPECIALIST. In *Conference Proceedings: Fostering Your Research Spirit* (pp. 484-486).

17. Raxmatovna, R. M. *Modern Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*.

18. Ismanova, O. (2023). NEMIS TILIDAN O'ZBEK TILIGA TARJIMA QILISHDA TARJIMON MAHORATI. *Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций*, 2(11), 93-97.

19. Urunbayevna, I. O. (2024). TARJIAMADA LEKSIK SINONIMLARNING O'ZIGA XOS KATEGORIYALARI. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 17(1), 182-184.

20. Urunbayevna, I. O. (2024). SO 'ZNING LEKSIK MANOSI VA MATNDA LEKSIK QO'LLANILISHI. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 17(1), 164-168.

21. Urunbayevna, I. O. (2024). TUSHUNCHA VA SO'ZNING O'ZARO MANSUBLIK MUNOSABATI. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 17(1), 160-163.

22. Urunbayevna, I. O. (2024). DUNYOVIY FANLARGA OID BO 'LGAN TERMINLARNING BUGUNGI KUNDAGI AHAMIYATI. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 21(1), 35-37.

23. Urunbayevna, I. O. (2024). NEMIS VA O 'ZBEK TILLARI TARJIMASHUNOSLIGIDAGI NAMOHANGLIK. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 20(3), 7-10.

24. Бердиева, Д. Х. (2020). СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЯ ЗАКЛАДОЧНЫХ РАБОТ В СИСТЕМЕ РАЗРАБОТКИ МЕСТОРОЖДЕНИЯ КАУЛЬДИ. *Экономика и социум*, (11 (78)), 504-508.

25. Qosimov, M. O., Toshtemirov, U. T., Berdiyeva, D. X., & Damlajanov, F. B. (2022). YER OSTI KAMERALARNI QOTUVCHI TO 'LG 'AZMALAR BILAN TO 'LDIRISH ISHLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH. *BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(9), 112-116.

26. Касимов, М. А., & Бердиева, Д. Х. (2021). Выбор оптимального варианта системы разработки на руднике Каульды. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(6), 235-240.

27. Касимов, М. А., & Бердиева, Д. Х. (2021). Выбор оптимального варианта системы разработки на руднике Каульды. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(6), 235-240.

28. Шведов, И. М., & Косимов, М. О. (2021). Сборник задач и упражнений по гидромеханике для практических занятий и самостоятельной работы.

29. Косимов, М. О., & Аскарлов, А. М. (2024). Пути Улучшения Производства Буро-Взрывных Работ На Месторождении «Кальмакыр». *International Journal of Formal Education*, 3(5), 299-304.

30. Одилович, Қ. М. (2024). ОЛТИН ҚАЗИБ ОЛИШ КОРХОНАЛАРИДА ТАШКИЛИЙ ФАОЛИЯТ-САМАРАЛИ БОШҚАРИШ ТИЗИМИНИНГ АСОСИ. *Scientific Journal of Actuarial Finance and Accounting*, 4(04), 126-133.
31. Косимов, М., Халкулова, Х., & Эрматов, Н. (2024). ГИДРОГЕОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ ОБСТАНОВКА НА КАРЬЕРЕ «КАЛЬМАКЫР». *Евразийский журнал технологий и инноваций*, 2(4), 52-58.
32. Kosimov, M., & Malyushenko, D. (2024). MITIGATION OF ENVIRONMENTAL HAZARDS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF DEPOSITS BY OPEN-PIT AND UNDERGROUND METHODS. *Collection of scientific papers «SCIENTIA»*, (April 5, 2024; Valencia, Spain), 121-124.
33. Бердиева, Д. Х. (2022). РАСЧЕТ НАГРУЗКИ НА ЗАКЛАДКУ В УСЛОВИЯХ МЕСТОРОЖДЕНИЯ КАУЛЬДЫ. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(6), 792-802.
34. Abdurakhmonova, Z. (2024). COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS OF STUDYING THE DEPENDENCE OF SANOGENIC THINKING ON PERSONAL CHARACTERISTICS AND BEHAVIORAL STRUCTURE. *Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций*, 3(1 Part 3), 74-81.
35. Abdurahmonova, Z. (2024). Experience of Assessment of Social-Psychological Factors Affecting The Development of Sanogenic. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(1), 1-7.
36. Zuhra, A. (2021). EXPERIENCE OF SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL INTERPRETATION OF SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF INDUSTRIAL THINKING IN RUSSIA AND FOREIGN COUNTRIES. *INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN INDUSTRY*, 9(3), 926-938.
37. Zuhra, A. (2022). THE SCIENTIFIC-THEORETICAL RESEARCH OF THE FEATURES OF PERSONALITY THINKING BY ORIENTAL SCHOLARS. *TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 47-52.
38. Abdurakhmonova, Z. (2024). THE RESULTS OF RESEARCH ON THE ROLE OF FAMILY RELATIONSHIPS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SANOGEN THINKING. *Евразийский журнал технологий и инноваций*, 2(1 Part 3), 156-162.
39. Ismanova, O. (2023). NEMIS TILIDAN O'ZBEK TILIGA TARJIMA QILISHDA TARJIMON MAHORATI. *Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций*, 2(11), 93-97.
40. Urunbayevna, I. O. (2024). TARJIAMADA LEKSIK SINONIMLARNING O'ZIGA XOS KATEGORIYALARI. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 17(1), 182-184.
41. Urunbayevna, I. O. (2024). SO 'ZNING LEKSIK MANOSI VA MATNDA LEKSIK QO 'LLANILISHI. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 17(1), 164-168.
42. Urunbayevna, I. O. (2024). TUSHUNCHA VA SO'ZNING O'ZARO MANSUBLIK MUNOSABATI. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 17(1), 160-163.
43. Urunbayevna, I. O. (2024). DUNYOVIY FANLARGA OID BO 'LGAN TERMINLARNING BUGUNGI KUNDAGI AHAMIYATI. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 21(1), 35-37.
44. Urunbayevna, I. O. (2024). NEMIS VA O 'ZBEK TILLARI TARJIMASHUNOSLIGIDAGI HAMOHANGLIK. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 20(3), 7-10.
45. Ibrohimjon o'g'li, A. Q., & Urunbayevna, O. I. (2022). NEMIS FRAZEOLOGIZMLARNING RIVOJLANISH TARIXI VA TARAQQIYOTI HAMDA O'ZBEK FRAZEOLOGIZMLARI BILAN QIYOSIY TAHLILI. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(10), 202-205.